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INNOVATION FOR TOMORROW: PROGRESS IN SAFE AND SUSTAINABLE CONCEPTS

ABSTRACT BOOK

1.09.P-Mo076 Transcriptomic and Metabolomic Responses of Juvenile Rockfish (*Sebastes schlegeli*) to Fiber-Shaped Polyethylene Terephthalate Microplastics

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Microplastics (MPs) are potentially harmful factors that are widely distributed in the aquatic environment. However, the molecular mechanisms underlying the toxicity of fiber-shaped MPs remain uncertain depending on size and type. Fiber-shaped MPs (Sizes: 200-400 μm , 3000 μm) made of polyethylene terephthalate (fPET) were exposed to juvenile rockfish (*Sebastes schlegeli*) at four concentrations (0.2, 2, 20, and 200 mg/L). And the toxic effects were assessed by cytotoxicity and oxidative stress, and the toxic mechanism were identified using transcriptomic and metabolomics analysis in rockfish exposed to microplastics for 20 days. The growth rate of rockfish decreased but activity of apoptosis and phagocytosis of leukocytes were increased after exposure of fPET. The enzyme activities of glutathione S-transferases and superoxide dismutase increased in the high-concentration MPs exposure group. The liver differential expression genes (DEGs) of rockfish exposed to fiber MPs of size 200-400 μm were related to lipid metabolic process, cellular component organization, cell differentiation, and response to stress. The DEGs of the liver of rockfish exposed to fiber MPs of size 3000 μm were related to steroid metabolic process, developmental growth, and cell differentiation. Metabolite analysis showed abundant arachidonic acid metabolism, biosynthesis of unsaturated fatty acids, and linoleic acid metabolism, which belong to lipid metabolic processes. These results might be show the fPET exposure related to process of the antioxidant system and homeostasis maintenance in juvenile rockfish. These results will be helpful in understanding the toxic effects and mechanisms in juvenile fish exposed to fPET.

1.09.P-Mo077 Plastic Debris in Mussels: Molecular Responses and Role in Okadaic Acid Uptake and Toxicity

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Plastic pollution poses a significant threat to marine ecosystems, particularly through the smaller fractions, namely microplastics (MPs) and nanoplastics (NPs). In addition to the toxicity associated with their direct exposure, plastic debris can also adsorb harmful biotoxins produced by microalgae. Microalgal cells can interact with or incorporate smaller plastics, potentially facilitating the transfer of these biotoxins into other marine organisms. Therefore, this study investigates the interactions between plastic debris and marine microalgae, evaluating their harmful effects on bivalve organisms from a trophic transfer perspective. Laboratory experiments were conducted to examine the transfer of NPs (0.1 or 1 μm) to mussels via microalgae. Additionally, the role of plastic debris ($\sim 5 \mu\text{m}$) in adsorbing the lipophilic okadaic acid (OA) toxin and serving as vectors for its transfer was assessed. Using confocal microscopy, flow cytometry, HPLC, and omic approaches, we analyzed the NPs accumulation and alterations induced by its exposure, as well as the accumulation and effects of the adsorbed biotoxin in the digestive glands (DG) and other tissues (OT) of mussels. We anticipate that microalgae will transfer particles of varying sizes differently, leading to significant proteomic changes in mussels. Furthermore, preliminary results indicate that after three days of exposure, significantly higher concentrations of OA were detected in the DG, increasing from $1.81 \pm 0.21 \text{ ng g}^{-1}$ on day 2 to $12.84 \pm 4.50 \text{ ng g}^{-1}$ by day 14 in mussels treated with MPs adsorbed with OA. While alterations in gene expression and differentially expressed proteins (DEPs) are still under analysis, our findings highlight the potential for OA transfer by 5 μm plastic particles and their associated toxicity. This work emphasizes the risks posed by MPs and NPs to trophic chain stability and safety, not only due to their direct action on aquatic organisms but also by highlighting the role of microalgae in inadvertently facilitating the transfer of harmful particles to higher trophic level organisms. This work was funded by the International Atomic Energy Agency (IAEA) via research contract PHYTOPLASTOX (RC #23548) and by the Coordination of Superior Level Staff Improvement (CAPES, Brazil) via a PhD scholarship granted to E.P. This work was also supported by the Portuguese Foundation for the Science and Technology (FCT) through the project NanoPlanet 2022.02340.PTDC, and UIDB/04423/2020 and UIDP/04423/2020 contracts. M.J.A. and A.C. also acknowledge the FCT funding for the Scientific Employment Stimulus Program (2023.06491.CEECIND and CEECIND/03767/2018, respectively).

1.09.P-Mo078 Harmonizing Data for Dietary Microplastic Exposure: Insights into Seafood and Age-Specific Risks

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Over recent decades, the rapid increase in plastic production has led to heightened concerns about the pervasive presence of microplastics (MPs) in the environment. Defined as particles smaller than 5 mm, MPs are increasingly detected in various food categories, raising questions about human exposure and associated health risks. This study aims to evaluate dietary exposure to MPs, with a specific focus on seafood, and to assess the contribution of various food groups to total MP exposure. To address this challenge, we reviewed existing data on MP occurrence in bivalves and crustacea and analyzed findings from a previous study involving 218 food items purchased from mainstream food retailers. We employed exposure assessment techniques to estimate daily MP intake across three age groups (children, adolescents and adults), considering realistic and worst-case scenarios. Special attention was given to aligning and comparing data from diverse sources using standardized methodologies. Our results indicate that adults have an average MP exposure of up to 0.37 MP per kilogram of body weight per day under realistic conditions. In contrast, children experience the highest exposure, reaching 4.19 MP per kilogram of body weight per day in worst-case scenarios. These findings highlight significant variability in exposure levels based on age and dietary habits. This study highlights the critical need for harmonized methodologies to synthesize data from diverse sources, particularly in evaluating seafood as a major contributor to dietary microplastic (MP) exposure. MPs in food may act as vectors, potentially transporting contaminants and allergens, making them more significant for secondary risks than nanoplastics (NPs), which are more concerning due to their distinct toxicological profiles. By improving our understanding of MP ingestion through food, this research provides a foundation for future investigations into exposure sources, associated health risks, and strategies for mitigation. The research that yielded MP occurrence results, was funded by the Belgian Federal Public Service Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment through the contract RT 18/05 Plastic in Food. The complementary study and the literature review was done in the scope of IMPTOX project which was funded by The EU's H2020 framework program for research and innovation, grant number 965173 entitled An innovative analytical platform to investigate the effect and toxicity of micro and nanoplastics (MNPs) combined with environmental contaminants on the risk of allergic disease in pre-clinical and clinical studies

1.09.P-Mo079 Effects of Micro(nano)plastics on Amphibian Cell Lines

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Plastic materials released into the environment undergo abiotic and biotic processes that cause the formation of microplastics (MP 100 nm to 5 mm) and nanoplastics (NP < 100 nm). The increasing reports of the effects of these particles on biota have driven the search for more sustainable alternatives such as bioplastics. However, whether bio-based plastics are more eco-friendly than conventional fossil-based plastics remains uncertain. There is thus the need to increase the knowledge regarding the effects of fossil- and bio-based plastic particles, particularly for organisms under high anthropogenic stress, such as amphibians. Due to ethical constraints, direct testing on these organisms is limited, and in vitro cellular models using established cell lines appear as a potentially valuable approach to assess the risks of MP and NP. This study assessed the effects of MP and NP from two fossil-based polymers polymethylmethacrylate (PMMA) and polystyrene (PS) and one bio-based polymer, polylactic acid (PLA), on two amphibian cell lines: A6 (adult *Xenopus laevis* kidney epithelial cells) and XTC-2 (tadpole *Xenopus laevis* carcass fibroblast cells). The cells were exposed to PMMA NPs (0 400 mg/L) and PS and PLA MPs (0 200 mg/L) and cell viability was assessed using the MTT assay (after 72-hour exposure). The ability to generate reactive oxygen species was assessed using the DCFDA assay (after 3-hour exposure), and the ability to cause DNA damage was studied through an alkaline comet assay (after 24-hour exposure).

PMMA NPs had no significant impact on cell viability for both cell lines, despite the ability to increase ROS production. In contrast, PLA MPs significantly affected A6 cell viability in the highest concentration tested whereas PS MPs had no significant effect. The highest concentration of PLA and PS MPs decreased XTC-2 cell viability. Overall, the ability of plastic particles to affect DNA integrity was also shown.

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1.09.P-Mo080 Adsorption and Protection of Environmental DNA (eDNA) on Polymer and Silica Surfaces